

Enforcing network connectivity in robot team missions

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Abstract

The growing interest in robot teams for surveillance or rescue missions entails new technological challenges. Robots have to move to complete their tasks while maintaining communication among themselves and with their human operators, in many cases without the aid of a communication infrastructure. Guaranteeing connectivity enables robots to explicitly exchange information needed in collaborative task execution, and allows operators to monitor or manually control any robot at all times. Network paths should be multi-hop, so as not to unnecessarily restrict the team range.

In this work we contribute a complete system which integrates three research aspects, usually studied separately, to achieve these characteristics: a multi-robot cooperative motion control technique based on a virtual spring-damper model which prevents communication network splits, a task allocation algorithm that takes advantage of network link information in order to ensure autonomous mission completion, and a network layer which works over wireless 802.11 devices, capable of sustaining hard real-time traffic and changing topologies. Link quality among peers is the key metric used to cooperatively move the robots and maintain uninterrupted connectivity, and the basis for novel ideas presented in each subsystem. Simulations and experimental results with real robots are presented and discussed.

Keywords: Cooperative Navigation, Link Quality Based Communication, Multi Robot Task Allocation, Networked Robot Systems.

1 Introduction

At present the size, complexity, or time constraints of many environments justify or impose the use of multiple mobile robots in the simultaneous execution of several workloads in a mission. Usually, these workloads are the result of breaking the mission down into tasks, according to spatial or specialization criteria which depend on the robots capabilities. For instance, the working area may be distributed among robots in order to build a global map, or several robots with different sensory capabilities

may be sent to the same target in order to obtain complementary information.

Another practical aspect is that many real world multi-robot applications involve only a small set of robots (no more than a dozen), normally supervised or partially telemanipulated by human operators working from a console. Communication among robots and with operators is required for most activities involving a robot team. This includes cooperative perception, cooperative navigation, working in overlapping areas, task allocation, interaction with operators, etc.

Wireless communications are needed in mobile robot teams to preserve mobility. However, in certain environments or applications, the communication infrastructure may be damaged or missing, for example in hostile environments, emergencies and rescues, disaster recovery, special events, battlefields, space, marine applications and so on. In such situations, communications must be explicitly dealt with, since their interruption may imply impaired team performance, loss of robots and, in the worst case, mission failure.

In the environments discussed, humans and robots self-organize in a Mobile Ad-hoc NETWORK (MANET). These networks are usually multi-hop, that is, nodes also act as routers, to increase coverage and to deal with changing network topology. Additionally, a MANET for robotic team applications must provide Hard Real-Time (HRT) traffic and connectivity guarantees. As is well known, all control applications have strict real-time requirements. In distributed control applications, such as those of robotic teams, the requirements extend to communications. In order to cooperate, robots must exchange information concerning both the environment and their own state. The real-time constraints of multi-robot applications have been recognized in the literature in, for example, (Facchinetti *et al.*, 2005), (Akyildiz and Kasimoglu, 2004) or (Franchino *et al.*, 2005). Real-time support is therefore a key feature. Furthermore, by acting on robot motion planning, communication losses can and must be prevented, since isolated robots disrupt cooperation, are out of supervision, cannot transmit information, and may be unable to rejoin the team even become physically lost.

In recent years there have been many developments in research and applications for mobile multi-robot sys-

tems. Many of these have focused on robot motion coordination aimed at fulfilling optimal criteria to accomplish goals. Other works have dealt with the maintenance of formations or structures, more or less flexible, adaptable whenever possible to environment constraints, while the team moves toward its goals. Another field of research has been task planning and multi-robot task allocation, for which several techniques and different criteria to be optimized have been proposed.

In the literature, the issues involved in a robot team are usually treated separately, in particular the robotic and the communication issues. However, in this paper we contribute a complete approach, capable of dealing jointly with such issues. This is achieved, in particular, by combining three modules within the system: a Cooperative Navigation Module (CNM), a Communication Module (COM), and a Multi-Task Allocation module (MTA). In addition, in the paper we provide novel techniques within each of the three integrated subsystems.

The CNM module clusters robots in a flexible formation, with one robot being the leader of the formation and the other robots being the slaves. Each formation is constituted as a MANET derived from the link qualities, causing the system to react in order to prevent network splits. The connections between robots are maintained by a model based on a spring-damper mechanical analogy. Connectivity is achieved by means of a multi-hop communication protocol with real-time capabilities, implemented by the COM module. Finally, in the MTA module we extend task allocation techniques to control the robot clusters, making the accomplishment of tasks compatible with the connectivity constraints.

Simulations and experimental results in real scenarios are described and discussed. The simulations were used to evaluate and select the best of the different techniques developed, which are analyzed by the use of certain proposed metrics. The experiments in real scenarios provided the opportunity to deal with real problems and assess the reliability of the system developed. The experiments were designed to highlight the core aspects of the present work, which are the problems arising in communications with robot mobility and the implications that the connectivity constraint has on motion planning for successfully completing missions. In this latter regard, homogeneous robots were used whose goals were to reach specific positions. The restrictions imposed on task allocation were related only to communications.

In the following section we present a brief review of related work on the techniques involved in this paper. In Section 3 a system overview is outlined. In Section 4 the cooperative motion control module is presented, and in Section 5 the Communication Module is described. Section 6 develops the task allocation techniques used in this system. In Section 7 implementation considerations required for working with real robots and systems are addressed. Section 8 discusses the results of simulations and real experiments. The paper ends with conclusions

and proposes future work.

2 Related work

In a multi-robot mission, distributed sensing, control and coordination are essential, and only possible if there are communication paths between all the nodes involved (robots and humans); in other words, if the communication network is connected. Usually, robot tasks entail movement, and this directly affects the communication network topology and hence the network connectivity. The question is how to control the motion of robots to accomplish the mission objectives while maintaining network connectivity. This fundamental issue has received little attention in the robotics literature, although it is now an emergent field in many works related to robotic missions in real scenarios. A good example is the DARPA Landroids initiative to autonomously cover areas with Wi-Fi (DAR, 2007).

In (Basu and Redi, 2004) movement control algorithms are proposed from the communication fault tolerance perspective. The idea is to maintain the network biconnected, that is, that there be always at least two alternate communication paths between each pair of robots. However, the problem is seen only from the network connectivity point of view, and the fulfillment of mission objectives is not taken into account. In (Rooker and Birk, 2004) the Frontier-Based exploration (the objective of the mission) algorithm is extended to deal with network connectivity. These works are limited to simulation and consider the communication range of robots in relation only to distance. This does not match reality, where the propagation model is more complicated because the signal depends not only on the distance, but also on the multiple paths from walls and obstacles. Moreover, communication links usually do not disappear suddenly, and their quality can be measured. In (Nguyen *et al.*, 2004) the signal quality is sensed. In this work, the objective is to maintain communication between a robot and a base-station. To accomplish this goal, a set of relay robots follows the lead robot. Each node monitors the radio link to the node behind it. When it drops below a preset threshold, the node stops and becomes a stationary relay node. Thus, to maintain communications a robot chain is deployed. In this work, relay robots only have the mission of maintaining communication links. This idea is generalized in (Mosteo *et al.*, 2009) with a focus on cost bounds for execution plans. In (Stump *et al.*, 2008) a similar objective is proposed. A framework is developed to control a team of robots that maintains and improves the communication between a stationary robot and another exploring robot. The other members of the team move maintaining a bridge between both robots, but only one task at a time is performed by the explorer robot. Moreover, no real signals are used and only simulation results are provided. In our work, the system measures real link quality and there are sev-

eral tasks that can be attempted simultaneously by the robots, which are always candidates to be relays. Several tasks are planned to be simultaneously accomplished by the robot team

Cooperating robots need to exchange data on the environment and their own state that is inherently time-constrained (Facchinetti *et al.*, 2005). Unfortunately, protocols for Ad-Hoc networks typically focus on issues such as maximizing throughput or minimizing average message delay, neglecting the indeterminism introduced. Moreover, most of the commercial low-level network protocols (e.g. 802.11, 802.15.4, etc.) do not provide timeliness guarantees on network transmissions due to packet collisions, exponential back-offs, and the false blocking problem (Ray and Carruthers, March 2003). Consequently, specific protocols aimed at eliminating indeterminism and supporting real-time traffic have been developed in recent years. In some solutions, a node that needs to transmit occupies the medium with pulses of energy (Sobrinho and Krishnakumar, 1996; Sheu *et al.*, 2004). The duration of the pulses is proportional to the priority of the node. In general, such solutions do not address the problem of the hidden terminal. Moreover, these solutions require hardware modification. In (Lee *et al.*, 2002) and (Donatiello and Furini, 2003) two token-passing based solutions are proposed. In these works, the network must have a ring topology and each node knows its successor and predecessor. However, the need to maintain the ring topology causes serious problems of mobility. Recently, in (Facchinetti *et al.*, 2005), the authors proposed another interesting solution at the MAC (Medium Access Control) level based on a time-division scheme to avoid collisions and using an implicit EDF (Earliest Deadline First) scheduling to provide real-time guarantees.

In our work, we used the RT-WMP protocol (Tardoli and Villarroel, 2007) which offers support for real-time traffic, priorities and multi-hop capabilities. This is based on a token passing scheme and can work with any network topology.

As well as the protocol used for communication, a system is needed to enforce that the link among robots is of sufficient quality. To that end, cooperative robot navigation must be employed to prevent robots from moving too far apart. There are several proposals for robot formation movement, and some of which use a spring model for motion. In (Reif and Wang, 1995) restricted potential fields were used for simulating spring forces and (Gulec and Unel, 2005) used graph theory, where the links between nodes are springs. Previous works only had the purpose of maintaining a topology or formation among the robots, but not maintaining network connectivity as proposed in our work. To deal with this problem, we have developed a spring-damper model to maintain connectivity among robots while simultaneously enabling them to perform the mission tasks.

Connectivity constraints add a new complexity to the already NP-hard (Gerkey and Mataric, 2004) task allo-

cation problem. Basic approaches opportunistically take advantage of network connectivity when available (Burgard *et al.*, 2005), but are not specifically intended to avoid network splits. To do this, a further possibility is to dictate task generation as well as task allocation. E.g., in exploration, goals may be decided as the result of cost functions that depend on signal quality (Vazquez and Malcolm, 2004; Rooker and Birk, 2006). This is difficult to carry over to more flexible service missions, since tasks are conditioned by external requirements (e.g. visiting an injured person, and in general visiting arbitrary goals), and thus the system cannot create tasks based on its preferences.

More general approaches, in which task generation is not a part of the solution and connectivity is an explicit requirement, are scarce. In (Wagner and Arkin, 2004) a behavioral approach can be found where connectivity maintenance is addressed, but is not treated as inviolable. In (Kalra *et al.*, 2007), a line-of-sight constraint is applied, but the actual link quality is not used.

The allocation method presented in this paper couples two advantageous aspects of those approaches: reactive allocation based on observed signal conditions, which is considered the critical constraint, and allocation of given tasks, suitable for a general purpose team not tied to a particular problem. Additionally, as part of our algorithm, we use switchable strategies derived from unconstrained approaches such as the Hungarian method (Kuhn, 1955), auction based heuristics (Mosteo and Montano, 2007) and travelling salesman heuristics (Reinelt, 1994). In (Mosteo *et al.*, 2008) the same multi-robot routing problem under communication constraints is treated, but focusing on alternative plan building strategies to those evaluated here.

As a continuation of this previous work, in this paper we further develop these techniques extending them to real scenarios, real robots, and using the actual signal quality as a constraint for the motion and the task allocation techniques. To this end, communication and cooperative motion control components are needed. This work deals with all these issues within a complete framework: mission accomplishment, communication connectivity in ad-hoc networks, and robot team cooperative motion. To our knowledge, such an integrated vision of the problem in multi-robot applications has not been presented before.

3 System overview

Our motivation is the envisioned prospect of mobile robot teams able to perform tasks in a versatile manner while automatically adapting to the communication network conditions, without dependence on external infrastructure. This solution is scalable to a relatively small set of robots (about 15 units). In this work, our system consisted of a set of robots equipped with wireless interfaces. Tasks were modelled as goals to be visited by one

Figure 1: Modules and information flows.

robot. The mission definition was to visit all the goals with any robot in minimum time, while the network remained permanently connected.

We started from the assumption that maintaining connectivity is a primary constraint *never to be violated*. This requirement introduces several other requirements. Firstly, multi-hop support is required in the underlying network to extend the coverage area. Secondly, control over the team movement strategy is needed to prevent robots from moving away and losing connectivity. Finally, a task allocation system has to be used to dynamically assign tasks to robots.

The approach is based on maintaining multi-hop routes between nodes of sufficient quality in order to avoid the network becoming disconnected. Thus, a measure of the communication link quality is needed. Based on this measure, the robot movements are restricted if necessary.

Our approach proposes a modular solution (Fig. 1), replicated in each robot:

- Cooperative Navigation Module (CNM): generates velocity commands for the robots, based on link qualities and robot goals. This controls the motions to avoid that no robot becomes disconnected.
- Communication Module (COM): provides multi-hop, real-time communication among robots, and also measures the communication link qualities among robots.
- Multi-Task Allocation module (MTA): assigns tasks to robots in such a way that ongoing mission progress is achieved while honoring network constraints.

The information flows between modules are depicted in Fig. 1.

The CNM module is responsible for preventing connectivity losses. It keeps the network connected using a coordinate motion strategy for all the robots. The solution is based on virtual Spring-Damper Systems (SDSs) among robots that change dynamically according to the quality of the communication network links. A set of virtual pulling forces produced by the current goals and

others generated by the SDSs as a function of the link quality between nodes and by the environment acts on the system in a coordinated manner controlling its motion.

The COM module fulfills the role of providing information transport. This module provides real-time traffic support. It also supports frequent topology changes while offering multi-hop capability. Finally, it provides both point-to-point delivery and efficient broadcast to network users. The network layer, however, is not location-aware, and the movement of the robots could cause connectivity losses due to the limited range of the wireless devices. This is a recurring feature even in relatively small environments. In fact the 802.11b range used in this work is usually considered to be about 150m outdoors, while in fact that distance can only be covered at 1 or 2 Mbps. At the maximum data rate, the distance is 45 meters at the most (Kapp, 2002). Consequently, if an application needs to rely on a certain bandwidth, this fact must be taken into account. The link quality among nodes is continuously monitored by the COM module, which provides a link-quality matrix to the CNM with this information.

The MTA assigns tasks to the robots in order that they visit all the goals in the minimum mission time. Since in spite of any given robot goals the CNM module never generates movements that would cause a network split, traditional allocation techniques cannot be readily applied. Hence, the MTA algorithm takes into account the CNM state to ensure compatible task allocations that will eventually lead to mission completion.

The Communication Module, besides providing the usual networking services, acts as a data source, supplying the Navigation module (CNM) with link qualities. The CNM additionally obtains the local robot pose and propagates it using the communication broadcast service. The Spring-Damper Systems, computed from links, and poses are supplied by the navigation module to the Multi-Task Allocation module, which computes goals that are sent back to the CNM and broadcast to other robots. The tight integration of the three modules should be noted. The modules are identical in all the robots; in this sense the system is decentralized. However, only one Multi-Task Allocation algorithm is active in providing goals for all the robots using global information, while the rest act as backups. In the case of failure of the robot that executes the allocation algorithm, any other robot would assume its role. The following sections explain the details of each module.

4 Cooperative Navigation Module

In this section we explain the Cooperative Navigation Module (CNM) for a team of robots. As described in Section 3, the aim of this layer is to provide a control for the robots to achieve their objectives while maintaining

Figure 2: Spring-damper model to maintain connectivity and motion coordination.

communication restrictions. We have developed a motion model based on a Spring-Damper System analogy (SDS). The forces generated on the SDS structure are responsible for the coordinate movement of the robots. The model is based on that presented in (Urcola *et al.*, 2008), adapted to the communication connectivity problem here dealt with. Let us briefly present this model.

4.1 Spring-damper model

First of all, we show an approximation of the model. Fig. 2 presents a simple structure of our system. This figure illustrates a team of four robots linked by SDSs. There are two types of robots, mobile and fixed. A fixed robot is, for example, a base station. We introduced the concept of fixed robot to support applications that need a static base station, for example, a computer that collects information from all robots or sends commands to them. The objective is to move the robots R_i to a goal using a virtual force \mathbf{G}_i whose module is computed as a function of the given leader's maximum desired velocity, and so it is *always bounded*. Due to the SDS which attaches two robots, a new force \mathbf{SD}_i will appear affecting both of them. The forces generated by the SDS for each robot are defined as:

$$\mathbf{SD}_i = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{sd}_{ij} a_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where A is a matrix whose elements a_{ij} represent the links between robots, and the force of a spring-damper link $\mathbf{sd}_{ij} = (sd_{ijx}, sd_{ijy})$ is computed as:

$$\mathbf{sd}_{ij} = k_s (\gamma - \gamma_0) \mathbf{d}_{\mathbf{u}} + k_v \mathbf{v}_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where k_s and k_v are the spring and damping coefficients, chosen to have a slightly overdamped behavior,

$\mathbf{d}_{\mathbf{u}}$ is the unit vector linking i, j robots, and \mathbf{v}_{ij} is the relative velocity between robots i and j . These values are calculated from the kinematic information provided by every robot, through the broadcast service of the COM layer (see Section 5). The value of γ is computed as a function of the link quality, s , so it does not represent the actual distance between robots, but a measurement used to establish the connection between each pair of robots when that quality decreases. The lower the link quality, the higher γ is. The γ_0 represents the rest value of γ . The link quality values are computed by the COM module from a Link Quality Matrix (LQM, explained in Section 5), describing the topology of the network. A median filter is applied to obtain s from the LQM values. After several tests we verified that a good function for γ is $\gamma(s) = k_s \cdot (s_{max} - s)$, s_{max} being the maximum link quality possible between two physically-coupled nodes, and k_s a constant computed from the maximum number of robots and the link quality thresholds explained below.

Since we want to model the behavior of a real system, we have to introduce a damping term \mathbf{D}_i on the robot forces defined by

$$\mathbf{D}_i = f_d \mathbf{v}_i \quad (3)$$

where f_d is the damping coefficient and $\mathbf{v}_i = (\dot{x}_i, \dot{y}_i)$ the velocity vector of the robot.

Moreover, the obstacles in the environment could enforce the robots to modify their relative location. This fact is included in the model by means of an external force \mathbf{E}_i on the robot R_i , always bounded to a maximum value. Summarizing, the total force \mathbf{F}_i on each robot is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{F}_i = \mathbf{G}_i + \mathbf{SD}_i + \mathbf{D}_i + \mathbf{E}_i \quad (4)$$

For this kind of application, this SDS model has several advantages over other approaches to coordinate the motion of robot teams. It adapts very well to the stated problem for several reasons. Firstly, this kind of model allows the robot team structure to be maintained considering the real kinodynamic constraints of robots, that is, realistic and feasible motions are computed, as we will see in the experiments. Secondly, the link to a task allocator system is direct, because it can assign tasks (i.e. goals) as attractive forces in a natural manner. Thirdly, influences of the environment are also very naturally included in the model as repulsive forces acting on each robot, adapting the motion to the dynamism or shape of the environment. Approaches based on graph models do not incorporate the management of the system dynamics in real situations, making it necessary to deal with dynamic behaviors using other additional models. The SDS proposed in this paper allows management of cooperative motion, taking into account the real dynamics of the robots and their connectivity, using a solution that involves a low computational burden.

In order to apply the computed forces calculated by

Figure 3: Theoretical function of the radio signal versus the distance between the transmitter and the receiver. When the radio has a value less than the safety threshold (st), it enters the Controlled zone where the spring-damper analogy is used to avoid network disconnection.

the SDS to each real robot, we use a Motion Generator for differential-drive mobile robots (the kind of robots used in the experiments). The Motion Generator transforms these forces (\mathbf{F}_i) into linear and angular velocities according to the equation:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{F}_i \quad (5)$$

By solving this differential equation we can obtain the linear and angular velocities $\mathbf{x}_i = (v, \omega)$, complying with the kinodynamic constraints of the robots. The parameters of \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Q} matrices are tuned to obtain an overdamped behavior, and to generate feasible trajectories for the real robots. Details about the model, stability issues, dynamic behavior, parameter tuning and adaptability to the shape and size of the environment can be found in (Urcola *et al.*, 2008), whose results are applicable to the adapted model explained here.

From the point of view of the applied forces, the worst case situation to achieve a mission using the proposed techniques occurs when all the robots involved in the mission form a chain from the base to a goal. This situation will be described in Section 6. If the goal is unreachable the spring-damper structures will suffer the maximum forces, the highest being the force of the SDS connecting the base and the first robot. As mentioned above, the parameter k_s is computed for this situation to avoid the link quality between the first robot and the base decreasing under a given threshold.

4.2 Building the virtual structure

When the link quality between two nodes is high, there is no reason to put a SDS between them. But when the link quality starts to decrease, it is necessary to act to prevent a possible link loss. To that end, SDSs are created in our system before the link quality reaches unsafe values. However, the use of a virtual spring-damper structure to link two nodes restricts the mobility of both, and should therefore be used only when really necessary. In fact, SDSs should be created only for those links that have a link quality less than the *safety threshold* (st) (Fig. 3) and only when really necessary to maintain

Figure 4: Spring-damper structure generated by the Prim-based algorithm with matrix of links generated for the minimum spanning tree.

the network connectivity. To select the set of necessary SDSs, we have used graph theory. Assimilating the network to a graph, where the nodes are the vertices, we fix the weight of the edges as follows: if a link has a quality greater than the safety threshold, its weight is zero. Otherwise, the weight is a function of the link quality. The lower the link quality, the higher the weight of the link. Then, we apply an algorithm based on Prim's Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) algorithm (Prim, 1957) to such a graph to obtain a spanning tree that contains the maximum possible number of zero-weight edges, and only the less weighty ones among the other edges. The latter are those corresponding to the link for which it is necessary to create a SDS.

Movement of the robots can imply changes in shared link-quality information and consequently a change in the resulting spanning tree. However, the position of the robots is a continuous function of time (i.e. there are no jumps), and the springs are always created in their rest length. This means that the force generated at the creation of the SDS is null. This fact guarantees that the system does not suffer from sudden forces so that smooth and feasible movements are produced.

This process is completely decentralized. In fact, since all the robots have the same information about the link qualities in the network, each robot can autonomously calculate the tree and, consequently, the structure of the resulting SDS.

5 Communication Module

As mentioned above, our solution needs information about the link quality among nodes and the dynamic state of each of the robots. Consequently, the communication module (COM) must be capable of providing the link quality between each pair of robots and transporting the kinematic information in a multi-hop network with real-time guarantees. Furthermore, message priority support is needed if multiple flows of information in the network are required (e.g. laser scans, camera images, etc.) to guarantee real-time requirements.

The link quality measurement or prediction is today a challenging question. Some estimators have been proposed such as RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indica-

tion), SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio), PDR (Packet Delivery Ratio), or BER (Bit Error Rate), (Vlavianos *et al.*, 2008). All of them have limitations. RSSI does not capture the amount of destructive interference on links. It is extremely hard to accurately compute the SNR because commercial hardware does not provide noise information while receiving packets, or simply provides no noise level information at all. The use of PDR involves a large latency for estimating the link quality (Souryal *et al.*, 2006), and the BER computation introduces significant overheads and is sensitive to bit sequences (Vlavianos *et al.*, 2008).

We use RSSI for estimating the link quality because commercial cards provide this measure directly (no overhead), and the use of a token passing protocol avoids interferences between the nodes of the network. This last assumption supposes that no other nodes outside the network can interfere with the communication. However, instantaneous RSSI or SNR estimators can have temporary peaks due to small scale variations in the multipath propagation. Thus filters, such as moving average or even Kalman filters (see for example (Farkas *et al.*, 2008)), must be used to smooth the link quality estimation. For this work we have used RSSI filtered with a moving average. Evidently any improvement in hardware and estimation techniques can be adopted in the proposed system.

We assume in this work that the robot team is moving in workspaces in which no sudden falls or changes in signal strength occur. In open and uncluttered environments, such as those selected for the experiments, the signal strength changes smoothly, and so the proposed techniques are able to enforce connectivity. In cluttered and confined environments (e.g. tunnels) complex propagation patterns occur and serious signal fading can appear. Additional strategies should be applied to move the robots in order to recover good signal quality. This is an ongoing work beyond the scope of this article.

In this work we have used the Real-Time Wireless Multi-hop Protocol (RT-WMP) (Tardioli and Villarrol, 2007) because it provides the real time multi-hop communication needed and a measure of the link qualities. However any other protocol supporting multi-hop traffic and an estimation of the link qualities can be used in the proposed system. An extension was made to the protocol to allow the multicast communication needed to disseminate kinematic information of the robots to all the nodes of the network.

5.1 The Real-Time Wireless Multi-hop Protocol

The RT-WMP is a novel protocol for MANETs that supports hard real-time traffic. To that end, in RT-WMP, end-to-end message delay has a bounded and known duration and the protocol manages the global static priorities of the messages. The RT-WMP supports multi-hop communication to increase network coverage. The

Figure 5: A hypothetical situation described by the network graph and the corresponding LQM. The hops sequence of the protocol is also shown.

protocol has been designed to connect a relatively small group of mobile nodes (about 15 units). It is based on a token passing scheme and is completely decentralized. The protocol manages topology changes through the exchange of a matrix containing the link quality among nodes. It can be run on commercial hardware without modifications. It is currently implemented using commercial low-cost 802.11 devices.

In RT-WMP each node has a transmission and a reception priority queue. Each message is identified by a priority level, and messages with the same priority are stored in FIFO order. The protocol works in three phases (Fig. 5): the *Priority Arbitration Phase*, in which nodes reach a consensus about which one holds the *Most Priority Message* in the network at a given time; the *Authorization Transmission Phase*, in which an authorization to transmit is sent to the node that holds the most priority message; and the *Message Transmission Phase*, which sends the message to the destination node.

The routing of authorization and data messages is based on the Link Quality Matrix, which keeps the estimation of the quality of the links between nodes in the network. This matrix is shared among the members of the network.

5.2 The Link Quality Matrix

To describe the topology of the network, RT-WMP defines a weighted network connectivity graph where weights are functions of the *radio signal* between couples of nodes, and are indicators of the *link quality* between them. These weights are calculated using a moving average of the instantaneous value of the Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) that is the received signal strength in a wireless environment, expressed in an arbitrary unit.

Each column of the matrix, the *Link Quality Matrix* (LQM), describes the link quality of any node with its neighbors. The nodes use this information to find a reliable path over which to send route messages or authorizations, and to choose the node to send the token to. The information contained in the LQM is shared among all nodes, since it travels with the token and reaches all members of the network in every Priority Arbitration Phase. The nodes are responsible for actualizing the corresponding column of the LQM to inform the other nodes of local topology changes. The information about

Figure 6: Example of a modified frame. All but the last field are used in the basic RT-WMP protocol. In the tail, kinematic information of the robots travels with the frame to reach all the nodes.

link quality with neighbors is obtained by promiscuously monitoring the medium in order to obtain the radio signal information provided by the network adapter and update the LQM.

5.3 Adding multi-cast capabilities

The RT-WMP as initially defined does not have a multi-cast capability. This means that, to implement our system, the information on the position of each node (that must reach all the other nodes periodically, see Section 7 for details) would have to travel in the network as unicast messages. In an n nodes network, this means that n^2 messages would be needed to disseminate the data throughout the whole network. Since this type of information must be exchanged frequently, the corresponding network load can be guaranteed by RT-WMP only for a small number of nodes. Moreover, all the traffic would be used up in this task and no bandwidth for other flows would be available. To solve this, we extended the protocol to allow transportation of small quantities of data in the *tail* of the frames (Fig. 6). In other words, at the end of the protocol frames we added a space that nodes can use to publish information that all the other nodes can read. In this way, the information reaches at least all the nodes in each Priority Arbitration Phase, implementing a sort of broadcast communication. In this system in particular, we divided the tail of the frames in n parts (n being the number of members of the network). In each part, each node publishes its kinematic variables, which all the other nodes can read when they receive a frame.

6 Multi-Task Allocation module

This is the software component responsible for allocating pending tasks to robots. For this work we have modeled tasks as a given set of goals to be visited by any robot. The inputs available to the Multi-Task Allocation module (MTA) are the poses of all robots and the current SDS set in use by the CNM. In turn, the MTA outputs a set of robot-goal pairings to be used by the CNM as attractors. Note that the MTA module has no influence over which SDSs exist. Instead, it reacts to SDS changes by generating compatible allocations. In the following discussion we will use the terms task/goal and cost/distance interchangeably.

Figure 7: Several task allocation related situations: • R_1 and R_2 are deadlocked by forces in equilibrium. • Let us suppose a faulty allocation policy, with robots abandoning their goal if a SDS is attached to them. R_3 could attempt to reach G_3 , but once its SDS appears, the goal would be abandoned and R_3 would move to R'_3 due to SDS pulling force. At R'_3 , the SDS is not needed anymore and disappears, so G_3 could be attempted again by R_3 . This cycle could repeat indefinitely. • Robots linked by SDSs in chain form (R_4 and R_5) have maximum reachability. • The resulting force of goal assignment and SDSs causes R_7 and R_8 to move to R'_7 and R'_8 . At that point, one of the two is able to move forward using the other as a relay: a chain will have been formed.

The use of SDSs introduces constraints that traditional allocation methods do not face. A key issue is that of *deadlock states*, in which no goal is ever reached due to SDS forces and faulty allocation. Deadlocks must be avoided because they can render the entire team useless (total deadlock involving all robots) or highly degrade its performance (partial deadlock involving some robots).

We can distinguish between two classes of deadlocks. On the one hand, equilibrium deadlocks happen when a standstill is reached between SDS forces and goal attractors (Fig. 7, R_1 and R_2). In this case, no robots are moving and no goal can be reached. On the other hand, dynamic deadlocks (or livelocks) appear when robots are moving, yet fail to complete any task (Fig. 7, R_3).

There are at least two approaches for solving this issue. The *on-line* approach would try to detect a deadlock once it occurs and adopt measures to escape from it. The *off-line* approach, which is used in this work, implements an allocation method that is, by design, deadlock-free.

Another point of concern, when there is a static base, is that maximum reachability is achieved with chain configurations (Fig. 7, R_4 and R_5). Inducing these configurations ensures the completion of tasks that are within team range.

To explain the MTA some concepts must be defined:

- A *cluster* is each set of robots that are connected, at any hop distance, by SDSs as currently reported by the CNM. Robots without SDSs attached form a trivial mono-robot cluster.
- A *supercluster* (S-cluster henceforth) is a set of clusters which are aggregated by the MTA algorithm, as

Algorithm 1 MTA algorithm.

Inputs: PendingTasks

```
1: Plan  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ ,  $S_{\text{MTA}}^t \leftarrow S_{\text{CNM}}^t$ 
2: while PendingTasks  $\neq \emptyset$  do
3:   if GoalsReached(Plan)  $\neq \emptyset$  then
4:     PendingTasks  $\leftarrow$  PendingTasks  $\setminus$  GoalsReached(Plan)
5:      $S_{\text{MTA}}^t \leftarrow S_{\text{CNM}}^t$ 
6:     Plan  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
7:   else if UnreachableTask(Plan)  $\neq \emptyset$  then
8:     PendingTasks  $\leftarrow$  PendingTasks  $\setminus$  UnreachableTask(Plan)
9:      $S_{\text{MTA}}^t \leftarrow S_{\text{CNM}}^t$ 
10:    Plan  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
11:   else
12:      $S_{\text{MTA}}^t \leftarrow S_{\text{MTA}}^{t-1} \cup S_{\text{CNM}}^t$ 
13:     if  $S_{\text{MTA}}^t \neq S_{\text{MTA}}^{t-1}$  then
14:       Plan  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
15:     end if
16:   end if
17:   if Plan =  $\emptyset$  then
18:     Plan  $\leftarrow$  Allocate(PendingTasks,  $S_{\text{MTA}}^t$ )
19:     Plan  $\leftarrow$  GreedyFill(PendingTasks, Plan,  $S_{\text{MTA}}^t$ )
20:   end if
21:   SendGoalsToCNM(Plan)
22: end while
```

we will see. A trivial S-cluster is formed by a single cluster.

- An *intertask timespan* is the time elapsed between the consecutive removal of two tasks (either by completion or ultimate abandonment if unreachable).

6.1 The allocation algorithm

We now present the complete MTA subsystem (see Algorithm 1). The intuition behind this algorithm is that robots linked by SDSs (clusters) have the same goal in order to avoid competing forces and thus equilibrium deadlocks. However, clusters change often, growing and shrinking as a result of robot movements and link quality changes. The changing of allocations of tasks to clusters could cause cyclic behaviors (Fig. 7, R_3). In order to prevent this, monotonically growing sets of clusters (S-clusters), which also share the same goal, are maintained within an intertask timespan: this ensures the absence of cyclic cluster formations and thus of dynamic deadlocks.

Variables

Plan is the robot-goal allocation. *PendingTasks* is the set of unvisited goals. S_{CNM}^t is the SDS set in use by the CNM at that moment. S_{MTA}^t is a SDS set local to the MTA that is used for cluster aggregation into S-clusters. Clusters, being directly derived from the S_{CNM}^t set, are each maximal SDS-connected subtree. S-clusters are conversely derived from the S_{MTA}^t set.

Initialization and main loop (lines 1–2)

The one-time initialization prepares an empty plan and a S_{MTA}^t set of SDSs matching the one reported by the navigation module. Then the main loop starts and only exits once all goals have been visited or discarded.

Goal completion (lines 3–6)

When a goal is reached, the pending tasks are updated, the SDS set of the MTA is reset, and the plan is voided. This is done in order to build a fresh plan with the new S-cluster configuration. Note that goal removal (either visited or abandoned) marks the end of the current intertask timespan, and is the only instance in which S-clusters are reset.

Discarding of unreachable goal (lines 7–10)

The same actions as in goal completion must be performed when a goal is considered unreachable. This can be detected because the necessary conditions are that a single S-cluster comprising all the robots exists, that the network topology is a chain and that all SDSs are at maximum elongation.

S-cluster maintenance (lines 11–15)

If no goal has been reached, the S_{MTA}^t is updated by merging any new links appearing in S_{CNM}^t . That is, S_{MTA}^t stores growing SDS sets that, in the worst case, will span the full network as a single connected graph. By the S_{MTA}^t updating (line 12), S-clusters are always a nonstrict superset of clusters. From this it follows that a robot belongs to a single cluster and S-cluster, and that a cluster is always fully contained in some unique S-cluster.

Note that SDSs memorized in MTA have no dynamic effect for the CNM, which moves robots according to its instantaneous SDS set S_{CNM}^t derived from Prim's algorithm.

Replanning (lines 17–20)

When the plan is void (either at the start or because of goal completion or S_{MTA}^t growth), a new one is computed. This is done by the *Allocate* subprogram. This is a swappable piece of code (conferring useful flexibility to the MTA) that must conform only to the following postcondition: *robots in a same S-cluster share the same goal*.

Otherwise, there are no limitations on this particular algorithm. Details about the specific allocation strategies we have implemented and tested are described in Section 6.3. Chains (Fig. 7, R_4 and R_5) are naturally formed as a result of using the same goal for all robots within a cluster (Fig. 7, R_6 , R_7 and R_8).

GreedyFill ensures that no robots are idle when there are fewer pending tasks than S-clusters: any S-cluster that has no goal after *Allocate* is assigned its closest goal in this subroutine.

Thus, these properties hold for each plan sent to the CNM:

1. Robots in the same S-cluster have the same goal.
2. Robots are never idle (without a goal).

We choose to reset the S-cluster set (lines 5,9) on goal completion because otherwise, once a S-cluster has covered the full team, it would remain so forever. This, coupled with the S-cluster goal sharing, would mean that only one task at a time would be executed. Resetting the S-clusters on task completion allows a new reallocation to be started with one S-cluster per cluster and more tasks being executed in parallel.

Goal transmission (line 21)

Finally, the goals are sent to the CNM for use in its subsequent movement generation.

6.2 Boundedness of intertask timespan

In order to show that the MTA algorithm achieves mission completion, we show that, from any configuration, at least one goal is always eventually reached or permanently discarded; i.e. intertask timespan is always bounded. Since one task is removed after each intertask timespan, a bounded intertask timespan implies a bounded mission timespan.

1. Equilibrium deadlocks cannot occur because of the use of a same goal within each cluster. (*Allocate* postcondition.)
2. Dynamic deadlocks cannot occur because of the use of a same goal within each S-cluster (*Allocate* postcondition) and the monotonically growing size of S-clusters within an intertask timespan (algorithm line 11), which prevents the repetition of S-cluster configurations.
3. All robots are moving towards some goal (*GreedyFill* postcondition). Two cases are then possible:
 - (a) All robots and base belong to a same S-cluster. Owing to SDS forces (Fig. 7, R_6 , R_7 and R_8), eventually they will form a chain if necessary. This chain has maximum reachability; either the single goal will be reached (algorithm line 3) or will be eventually discarded (algorithm line 7). In either case, the intertask timespan ends and we are done. ■
 - (b) There are two S-clusters or more. By definition, only one S-cluster can include the static base (no node can belong to two S-clusters). Thus, all but this S-cluster are free to move unconstrainedly away from the base at this time in pursuit of their goals. At this point only two events can develop:
 - i. An S-cluster reaches its goal without growing (i.e. without new network constraints appearing), and we are done. ■

- ii. Two S-clusters are sufficiently apart to force a new SDS to appear. These S-clusters are merged, becoming a new larger S-cluster. At this moment we are back to point 3, but note that the monotonically growing size of S-clusters within an intertask timespan makes this occurrence bounded by the number of robots.

In summary, either some S-cluster reaches its goal, or eventually a single S-cluster that comprises all robots plus base is formed. This final S-cluster, which in the worst case is a chain, is either able to reach its goal or to diagnose an unreachable goal to be discarded.

6.3 Allocation strategies

We describe here four tested implementations for *Allocate* (algorithm line 18). For the following descriptions, let SC_t be the number of S-clusters at time instant t , when the subroutine is invoked. See Fig. 14 for a snapshot of each strategy execution in the Stage (Gerkey *et al.*, 2003) simulator. The term *gathering* in the following descriptions refers to the fact that the strategy tries to keep robots together by assigning close tasks.

Hungarian based. The well-known Hungarian method (Kuhn, 1955) computes the optimal pairing of tasks/workers. It only assigns one task per worker, leaving any excess tasks as pending for future allocation. We applied it to S-clusters instead of robots to respect the *Allocate* postcondition.

MinMix. MINMAX and MINSUM are two common objective functions for multi-robot teams: the former measures the worst robot cost, while the latter measures the sum of all robot costs. The MINMIX objective (Mosteo and Montano, 2007) showed good properties for general-purpose robotics in some of our previous research, and so we tried it here. It uses a balanced linear combination of the MINMAX and MINSUM costs to drive the assignation. In this work the algorithm was adapted and the insertion heuristic (Reinelt, 1994) is applied using S-clusters instead of robots.

Greedy with gathering. Let P be the pairing robot-goal of minimum cost, which is allocated for starters (hence the greediness). S-cluster mates of the robot in P also receive that goal. Then, the previous Hungarian based method (see Section 6.3) is applied to the remaining S-clusters, considering *only* the $SC_t - 1$ closer goals *to the one in P* .

TSP with gathering. This algorithm is the only one with a persistent component. While the others always reallocate remaining tasks from scratch, this one will compute on its first run a traveling salesman solution for the one robot with a closest goal.

This solution, computed with the insertion heuristic, is kept. Then, and in each subsequent call, the first SC_t pending goals of this persistent solution are allocated using the Hungarian-based method to the SC_t S-clusters. The idea behind this algorithm is to investigate how useful global planning is in this highly dynamic and reactive system.

7 Temporization issues

To compute the cooperative movement based on the spring-damper analogy, nodes have to share their kinematic information (absolute pose and velocities) to compute the forces acting on the system using the same set of data. However, due to the distributed nature of the system and the communication needed to share these data, a perfect synchronization is not possible and thus robots have to work with slightly different information. The time-displacement among kinematic data on different robots must be sufficiently short to guarantee a correct system dynamic. The task of propagating the shared data is carried out by the broadcast service of the COM module. In fact in each iteration of the control loop, the latter publishes its kinematic information (pushing it in the RT-WMP queue) that is propagated by the network. This introduces a (known) propagation delay t_p that can be calculated as (Tardioli and Villarroel, 2007):

$$t_p = (4n - 8)t'_i + (n - 2)t'_a + (n - 2)t'_m \quad (6)$$

n being the number of nodes, t'_i the time needed to send a token of the RT-WMP protocol considering the extra data in the tail, t'_a and t'_m the time needed to send an authorization and a message respectively, in the same conditions. However, in the worst case, a node could have to wait the same amount of time before being able to send the data (if it has just sent its previous actualization), thus the actualization time must be considered as $t_{act} = 2 \cdot t_p$. Nevertheless, when a node receives fresh data from the network, it is stored in the RT-WMP broadcast queue up to the moment in which the control loop pops it to compute a new system status. Thus, the information can wait in the queue up to a whole control loop period T_{cl} before being used. Taking into account all these terms, the time displacement in the shared data with which any control loop (except the local one) works in any iteration can be $t_{disp} = T_{cl} + t_{act}$ in the worst case. On the other hand, the time-displacement between the most recent pose information provided by the hardware, and the data with which any local control loop is working in any iteration (and that it sends to the other robots) can be, in the worst case, equal to the control loop period if, as in our system, both events are not synchronized. This can happen if the control loop reads the information just before the moment in which the microcontroller updates the data. This fact must be taken into account when

Figure 8: Evolution of the robots movement and links created between them.

choosing the control period to guarantee a strict concordance between the reality and the control-loop view of the reality and allow a correct behavior of the system. In our system, the hardware provides new pose information each $T_{\mu c} = 100ms$ and the control loop iterates with the same period ($T_{cl} = 100ms$). For the network considered in this paper (4 nodes network, 11Mbps data rate and maximum data unit of 1500 bytes for unicast messages and 14 bytes per robot of kinematic information), the value of the propagation time is $t_p = 6.05ms$ and thus $t_{act} = 12.1ms$. This implies that we are guaranteeing a maximum time displacement of $t_{disp} = 112ms$ approximately. The maximum time-displacement between hardware data and control loop data is, instead, about $T_{local.hw.disp} = T_{\mu c} = T_{cl} = 100ms$ for the local node and $t_{remote.hw.disp} = T_{disp} + T_{cl} = 212ms$ for the remote nodes, in the worst case.

Notice that the value of t_{act} depends on the number of nodes, on the maximum data unit for unicast messages and on the data rate. As an example in a 10-nodes and 54Mbps-data rate network, its value is about 30ms.

These values are completely assumable by the system since the dominant dynamic time constant of the system is about one second.

8 System evaluation

To evaluate our system we performed a set of simulations and a set of experiments with real robots. For the simulations, we chose the Player/Stage platform (Gerkey *et al.*, 2003) in which it is possible to simulate our real Pioneer P3 robots. We carried out three types of experiment: the first, to verify the correct joint working of the COM and CNM modules; a second type, where task allocation strategies were evaluated; finally, the whole system was tested in real scenarios.

8.1 Communication and cooperative navigation experiments

The objective of this set of tests was to verify the correct behavior and the validity of the spring-damper model proposed, without taking into account the MTA module at all. The idea was to put a base station (BS) and three robots (R_1 , R_2 and R_3 which is the head robot) in

Figure 9: Linear velocity during the simulation and evolution of the relative distances between consecutive robots.

a chain a few meters apart from each other and assign a goal to the robot at the head of the chain. The correct behavior of the system is that in which the head of the chain moves freely up to the moment when the link quality between it and its successor reaches the threshold of the controlled zone (Fig. 3). At that moment, a SDS should be created by the system between these two robots. The second robot starts to move also pulled by the SDS up to the moment when the same situation occurs with the third robot. On the other hand, the base station is fixed and the system should either lengthen to allow the head robot to reach the goal, or a stall situation would occur if the head robot cannot reach the goal (due to the insufficient lengthening of the SDSs). We reproduced this experiment in simulation and in a real environment. The results of these experiments are presented in the following sections.

8.1.1 Distance based simulation experiment

The Player Stage platform allows the simulation of robots in a simulated environment using our independent code in each robot. The user code is the same as that used in real robots. However, since simulation implies the use of virtual robots running on desktop machines (and therefore not mobile), the use of a real LQM was not possible. As a consequence, the simulation was performed using a function of the distance between the simulated robots instead of the link quality. These tests allowed us to verify the correct implementation of the system. Results are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. In t_1 the distance between R_3 and R_2 reached the rest length of the virtual spring and the first SDS was created. Consequently, the speed of the head robot decreased and R_2 started to move. In t_2 the same event occurred with R_2 and R_1 , and the speed of R_3 also changed. Finally, in t_3 the third SDS between R_1 and the base station (fixed robot) was created. All the robots began to decrease their speed until reaching a complete stop.

Figure 10: Snapshots of the robots during the experiment.

8.1.2 Distance based real experiment

We reproduced the same experiment already performed by simulation, in a real environment using three Pioneer 3 robots (Fig. 10). The experiment is shown in Extension 1. The robots were equipped with an on-board PC with a Pentium III processor at 800MHz and a 802.11b Cisco 350 Series wireless card. The robots were also equipped with differential GPS to provide accurate knowledge of their own positions. Results are shown in Fig. 11. Despite the noise introduced by the GPS and other equipment (e.g. the compass for orientation), the results were similar to those obtained by simulation.

8.1.3 Link quality based real experiment

The same experiment was performed with the sensed link quality among nodes. In this case we used the function γ of the link quality (the better the link quality, the lower the function). The results are shown in Fig. 12. Evidently, the graphs are noisier than the two preceding ones, due to the fluctuation of the radio signal among nodes. Fig. 12 clearly shows the moments at which the SDS were created by the system. In t_1 the value of $\gamma(s)$ between R_3 and R_2 increased and passed beyond the threshold causing the first SDS to be created. The robot R_2 started to move. At t_2 robot R_1 started to move after the link $R_2 - R_1$ overcame the threshold. The delay between this event and t_2 was due to a temporary good link between R_2 and the base station (not reported in the graph to avoid confusion) that caused the creation of an alternative multi-hop route and allowed R_2 to move

Figure 11: Linear velocity and distance during the real experiment and evolution of the relative distances between consecutive robots.

Figure 12: Linear velocity and evolution of the $\gamma(s)$ among robots during the link quality based real experiment.

a little before the creation of the SDS that linked it with R_1 precisely at t_2 . This fact shows clearly that in some situations the link quality among nodes is not directly related to the distance. Between t_2 and t_3 both links were stable (that is $\gamma(s)$ were over the threshold for both SDSs) and velocities of R_1 , R_2 and R_3 were more or less constant, despite a little oscillation. At t_3 $\gamma(s)$ for the R_1 -base link (that grew rapidly during the movement of the system) reached the threshold and caused the third SDS to be created and the stopping of R_1 . At the same time, links R_2-R_3 and R_2-R_1 reached a similar γ value and thus a null result force. This fact caused the slowdown of R_2 until a complete stop at around t_4 that in turn caused a slowdown of R_3 . After that, fluctuation of the radio signal among robots caused further movements until a complete stop occurred at t_5 due to force equilibrium. A temporary signal quality improvement between R_1 and base provoked an R_1 advancement, allowing R_3 to reach the goal at t_5 . As can be deduced from the experiment, using the link quality against distance provides a different behavior, so the use of distance to create

robot connections does not work. Another conclusion is that the SDS model is well adapted to controlling the dynamic system motion in real situations providing, in this aspect, similar results to those obtained by simulation.

8.1.4 Effect of obstacles on the link quality

To verify the effect caused by the presence of obstacles and the absence of line-of-sight on our system, we performed an experiment in an indoor environment, shown in Fig. 13. We used two mobile robots and a fixed base station and recorded the link quality among robots and base station. The goal of the experiment was to move the robot R_2 away from R_1 in a corridor and observe the behavior of the link quality and the behavior of the robots when the mobile robot turned around a corner and entered a room (see Fig. 13). As can be seen in Fig. 13.e, the function of the link quality ($\gamma(s)$) between R_1 and R_2 remained more or less constant up to the moment in which R_2 started to turn to enter the room (t_1). At this moment, in fact, the line of sight between

Figure 13: Evolution of the link quality in an indoor environment.

the antennas of R_2 and R_1 was partially cut off by the laser head of the former. The function γ grew and an SDS was created between both robots at time t_2 (fig. 13.b). At this moment R_1 started to move to reestablish a good link quality with the leader robot. Despite the movement, $\gamma(s)$ between R_2 and R_1 continued growing because R_2 entered the room (t_3). Nevertheless, the $\gamma(s)$ between R_1 and the base station grew very slowly (there still being line of sight between them) up to the moment (t_4) at which the threshold was reached and a second SDS was created by the system (fig. 13.c). After that both robots started to slow down because the pulling forces imposed by the SDS and the respective γ functions oscillated a little around the equilibrium point. At this moment the robots could not move forward without loss of communication with the base station.

8.2 Task allocation simulations

The purpose of this set of simulations, which comprised several tests, was to evaluate the allocation strategies described in Section 6.3. The tests had in common a set of eight mobile robots and a static base, located at the bottom-left origin in the scenario. In all cases, the robots were initially placed abreast in line formation on top of the base, and fifty goals were randomly placed in the XY-positive quadrant. The mission to accomplish was to visit all the goals, and total time was measured.

Three scenarios were tested. A long-range one, in

which goals were placed at a maximum range of nr (n being the number of mobile robots and r the SDS rest length), in order to test performance in extreme conditions; a short-range one where the maximum goal range was $\frac{nr}{2}$, in order to test performance when robot supply is ample in respect to the scenario size; and an intermediate one where goals were placed at a maximum range of $\frac{3nr}{4}$. In all cases, the SDS rest length was set at four meters, as if using low power radios while requiring good signal quality.

In addition, these tests were also run without any SDS constraints, as if the network range were infinite. In this case, since no SDSs appear, each robot is a trivial S-cluster. Additional runs with sparse random obstacles were also run to evaluate their impact on execution time.

Fig. 14 shows a snapshot of the four strategies running in the simulator in the medium range test. Ten runs were performed for each scenario, using unique random seeds. In each scenario, all strategies were tested using the same seed and thus on equal grounds. Simulations using all the strategies are shown in Extension 2.

Fig. 15a summarizes the time results. In the short-range test we observed a small time penalty due to network constraints when compared to unconstrained runs. However, the strategies followed the same trends in all cases, the non-gathering ones –Hungarian and MINMIX– being the best performers in both constrained and unconstrained runs. This is understandable, since in the short-range scenario there is less area to cover, and thus

Figure 14: Snapshots of simulation runs for the allocation strategies. Solid lines linking robots indicate S-clusters, while dashed lines from robots to goals indicate assignments. Absent X in some snapshots are already visited goals. Hollow squares are obstacles. In a) it can be seen that robots do not attempt to remain close to one another, and only one task per robot is allocated. In b) can be seen the complete MINMIX plans for each S-cluster. In c) can be seen the greedy pairing P and how all the remaining allocated tasks are the closest ones to the task in P . In d) can be seen the global TSP solution and how the first tasks in it are assigned to S-clusters.

fewer SDS occurrences. Hence, strategies without gathering do not artificially constrain robot spreading.

The time penalty was greater in the middle-range test. It affected the non-gathering strategies in particular, in a trend that was even more pronounced in the long-range test. We saw that the strategies that performed better in the unconstrained runs no longer did so in the medium and long range tests. When range to base is greater, it becomes more difficult to maintain many S-clusters executing tasks in parallel. Gathering strategies are able to keep more S-clusters for longer periods, speeding up mission execution. This is evidenced by the lower count of S-cluster changes in Fig. 15b. Gathering strategies also incur a smaller time penalty when compared to the unconstrained runs.

The same figure offers insights into other properties of the strategies. It evidences that the greedy strategy

may wildly change the tasks assigned from one allocation to the next (high count of preemptions). This does not translate into decisive time penalties, which suggests that preemptions are a secondary factor in mission time when compared to S-cluster changes. The Hungarian method, being locally optimal, is less prone to cause highly differing allocations.

Using a long-term plan (TSP strategy) has the additional effect of noticeably reducing preemptions. This is a consequence of trying always to allocate the same tasks in time-nearby allocations. Any time penalty linked to preemptions is thus mitigated with a global plan. We can also note that the TSP strategy has the lowest count for both preemptions and changes, apart from being the quickest (median-wise) once the range is not short. This suggests that other kinds of global plans are worth investigating in conjunction with our spring-damper scheme.

Figure 15: Data from task allocation simulations. In a) boxplots show quartiles of the regular experiments. Stars and squares show the average of experiments without springs and with obstacles, respectively, for comparison. b) shows task preemptions and S-cluster changes over the full mission. c) shows the time histogram for one execution of each strategy in the medium range scenario.

Finally, Fig. 15c highlights that average task concurrency is good. For economy of space this issue is not discussed further here.

8.3 Experiments with the whole system

The last experiment was intended to test the whole system behavior in a real scenario using the real link quality signal to maintain connectivity. It is shown in Extension 3. The objective was to complete a mission by visiting a set of goals with a team of robots. Twelve goals were placed to be visited by three GPS equipped Pioneer 3 robots supervised by a fixed base station (in this case a laptop). For the MTA layer we chose the Hungarian strategy because we expected the signal quality to be in the short/medium range scenario of the simulations. In these ranges, either Hungarian or TSP were expected to perform comparably.

Fig. 16.a shows the paths followed by the robots, and three superimposed snapshots of the existing SDSs at different times. Fig. 16.b shows the quality of the links that form the Minimum Spanning Tree of the communication network (see Section 4). The tree is composed of the minimum number of links with the maximum quality that are indispensable for maintaining the network connectivity. The three plots of the figure correspond to the three necessary links in this case. As can be seen, the links in the spanning tree change during the experiment depending on the relative quality (note the changes in the line types in all the plots). When the quality of a link of the spanning tree overcomes the threshold, a SDS is created (instants t_1 , t_2 , and t_3). No active link exceeded the forbidden threshold; thus, as intended, no active link was ever broken, which fulfills our objective of enforcing connectivity. Finally, Fig. 16.c shows the distances between all nodes. Here we can observe that distance and quality do not perfectly correlate, which suggests that using distance as a substitute for quality will not always provide the desired results.

Studying the three graphs at once, we can go into the

details of how things happened. Prior to t_1 , there was no need for SDSs, and there were several link switches that did not affect the team movements. At t_1 appeared the first SDS, linking base to R_2 . However, since all the robots were at a comparable distance to base, link quality changes prevented any strong preference for one of them as a relay, and thus we can observe that the base used for short periods of time any of the three robots as a relay for the other two. Eventually, R_1 lagged behind and consolidated as the stable relay between base and R_2, R_3 . When these robots moved away from R_1 , eventually a new relay was necessary: at t_2 , R_2 was linked with a SDS to R_1 . Finally, at t_3 a third SDS appeared when R_3 took the lead towards the farther goal.

We can observe that, with the parameters used, SDS were quite short when created (circa 10m) but the robots still retained a good level of mobility as the SDS elongated. It was not until shortly before t_2 , as link quality decreased, that R_1 was stopped by the SDS force pulling from base. Also, R_2 did not stop moving (Fig. 16.c) until the very end of the mission, which reveals that its SDS to R_1 was not yet at equilibrium. This shows that using distance as the SDS trigger would be difficult: either we could err by being too conservative, or we could try to allow more mobility and lose connectivity due to signal oscillations. Since different environment conditions could greatly change the expected maximum length of a link, this again confirms that using link quality is a better approach.

Task allocation worked as expected given the SDSs at each time instant. Since the MTA worked as has been described previously, we do not go into more detail in this respect.

The objective is achieved: the mission has been completed with a low time penalty while obtaining a good quality of communication at all times.

Figure 16: a) Paths followed by the robots and SDS at the time of their creation. b) γ of the links composing the Minimum Spanning Tree of the network during the complete experiment. c) Distances to base and between robots.

9 Conclusions

In this article we have presented a complete system that enforces communication connectivity in multi-robot missions, such as rescue or surveillance. Our approach proposes a modular solution: a Communication Module, a Cooperative Navigation Module and a Multi-Task Allocation module. The Communication Module offers real-time multi-hop communication to the robot team. The Cooperative Navigation Module deals with the coordinated movement of the robots using a physical analogy to a Spring-Damper System; this prevents disconnection of the network through the monitoring of the link quality among nodes. The Multi-Task Allocation module guarantees, within the current restrictions imposed on the problem, the completion of the team tasks while aiming for minimization of mission time. Tasks are reactively reallocated to adapt to the changing communication network topology, taking advantage of the clusters naturally formed by the dynamics of the cooperative navigation module. Several high-level allocation strategies were tested, concluding that for medium and

long-range missions a global plan and keeping robots together are advantageous. This minimizes changes in network topology and task preemption, thus allowing better task parallelization.

The whole system has been implemented and tested by means of simulations and real multi-robot experiments. Results show that the proposed solution fulfills the objective of maintaining network connectivity at all times while completing the assigned tasks. From the experiments we verify that the use of the link quality information, together with a virtual Spring-Damper System, is a valid solution for maintaining network connectivity even in the presence of obstacles and absence of line-of-sight.

Estimation of link quality is an open field of research, and any new result in this field will improve the behavior of this system. The navigation and allocation techniques are being extended to allow for more complex obstacles than those considered so far.

To conclude, we have developed a solution that integrates communications, motion coordination and task allocation, which are usually treated in isolation. In addition, in the paper we have described novel techniques

for each of the three integrated subsystems.

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Appendix: Index to Multimedia Extensions

The multimedia extensions to this article are at: <http://www.ijrr.org>.

Table of Multimedia Extensions

Extension	Type	Description
1	Video	Spring-damper (SDS) motion control of a team of robots.
2	Video	Multi-robot task allocation simulations using 4 allocation strategies under communication constraints.
3	Video	Multi-robot task allocation experiment enforcing network connectivity using the whole system.

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